

Table 2. List of the total captures of the three beneficial arthropods groups investigated (Mean $\pm$ SD). (GT-ECO Ground trap with EcoSordidina; PT-GEL pitfall trap with Cosmogel; PT-PLUS Pitfall trap with Cosmoplus). Different letters indicate difference between treatments (LMM, least-square means method, $p < 0.05$).

		Bento			Pedro		
		Total	Mean	SD	Total	Mean	SD
<i>Cosmopolites sordidus</i>	PT-GEL	926	(28,06 $\pm$ 40,11)	a	765	(44,06 $\pm$ 32,64)	b
	PT-PLUS	341	(56,45 $\pm$ 42,86)	c	1454	(59,79 $\pm$ 44,40)	d
	GT-ECO	1863	(10,33 $\pm$ 12,33)	e	1973	(23,18 $\pm$ 16,66)	f
Staphylinidae	PT-GEL	683	(20,70 $\pm$ 26,80)	a	574	(17,39 $\pm$ 19,27)	b
	PT-PLUS	732	(22,18 $\pm$ 41,32)	a	562	(17,03 $\pm$ 44,49)	a
	GT-ECO	19	(0,58 $\pm$ 1,12)	b	55	(1,67 $\pm$ 5,19)	a
Carabidae	PT-GEL	45	(1,36 $\pm$ 2,68)	a	49	(1,48 $\pm$ 1,33)	b
	PT-PLUS	26	(0,79 $\pm$ 0,89)	b	19	(0,58 $\pm$ 1,38)	a
	GT-ECO	4	(0,12 $\pm$ 0,33)	b	8	(0,24 $\pm$ 2,05)	a
Araneae	PT-GEL	25	(0,76 $\pm$ 0,79)		39	(1,18 $\pm$ 1,38)	
	PT-PLUS	21	(0,64 $\pm$ 0,93)		51	(1,55 $\pm$ 1,33)	
	GT-ECO	13	(0,39 $\pm$ 0,56)		66	(2,00 $\pm$ 2,05)	

Different letters indicate difference between treatments (LMM, least-square means method, $p < 0.05$).